

PHENET POLICY BRIEF 2024

1. PHENET SCOPE AND AIMS

PHENET, a 5-year Horizon Europe project, is designed to be a key driver for the agroecological transition in support of food security, climate change resilience, biodiversity, and soil carbon stock restoration in Europe. Four world-class research infrastructures (RIs), AnaEE, eLTER, ELIXIR, and EMPHASIS, join their forces to co-develop, with a diversity of innovative European companies, new tools and methods around agroecosystem phenotyping and envirotyping – meant to enrich the service portfolios of the RIs well beyond the project. Their new service portfolios will support the identification of future-proof combinations of plant species, genotypes, and agroecological management practices to meet the challenges of climate change and agroecological transition across Europe. These next-generation technologies include autonomous, low-cost, and low-energy sensors leading to new earth observation services to capture plant, soil, agricultural, and ecosystem data in thousands of locations simultaneously, supported by innovative Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Internet-of-Things (IoT) approaches to organise and make the best use of the resulting massive data.

2. PHENET CONTRIBUTIONS TO KEY EUROPEAN POLICIES

Moving towards its aims, PHENET supports key political agendas in Europe, ushering in transformative changes to overcome the challenges of climate change and environmental degradation. In supporting the Green Deal, PHENET will help transform the EU into a resource-efficient and competitive economy with zero net greenhouse gas emissions and economic growth, decoupled from resource use.

EU Food 2030 & Farm2Fork:

- PHENET positions itself at the forefront of innovation by leveraging next-generation technologies to develop agricultural practices and shape climate-smart food systems while preserving natural resources, boosting biodiversity, and ensuring resource efficiency.
- In co-developing its technologies with innovative European companies, PHENET lays the ground for new competitive business models and products around sensors, AI, IoT, Earth observation, and data interoperability.
- The distributed nature of the four RIs across Europe places PHENET at the epicentre of the location and regional innovation systems, fostering agroecological empowerment for communities across Europe.

EU Biodiversity Strategy:

- PHENET Earth observation technologies will enable highly efficient mapping and monitoring of protected and potentially protected areas, including the EU's primary and old-growth forests. This supports the effective management of these areas and aligns with the EU's goal of protecting a minimum of 30% of its land area by 2030.
- PHENET technologies will enable farming practitioners to effectively adopt agroecological practices and monitor progress in sustaining biodiversity, aiming to minimize environmental impact while maintaining and increasing yields.
- PHENET soil-related observation technologies will help assess soil fertility and soil erosion and monitor the effects of mitigation measures towards restoring soil ecosystems.

Strategic Research Agenda of the Joint Programming Initiative on Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change (FACCE-JPI)

- By enabling the enhanced monitoring and prediction of carbon flux components, including soil carbon retention, greenhouse gas emissions, and several underlying processes, PHENET technologies address game changers for climate neutrality of the agricultural sector.
- By providing tools for future-proof crop varieties and assessing agroecological management practices, PHENET will support innovative plant breeding technologies and the diversification of farming systems in line with the agroecological transition of agriculture.
- By enhancing the interoperability of multi-scale observation data, PHENET supports improved agricultural management practices towards less impact on ecosystems and, thus, nutrition-sensitive agricultural production.
- By improving the sharing of knowledge on agriculture and ecosystems with various stakeholders, such as policymakers and practitioners, PHENET helps to reduce trade-offs between food production, ecosystems, and climate.

EU Bioeconomy Strategy:

- PHENET observation and data interoperability technologies will contribute to a European-wide monitoring system to assess environmental sustainability and help manage resilient and healthy ecosystems.
- The integration of PHENET technologies into local innovation ecosystems via the facilities of the four RIs will unlock further innovation potential by supporting the development of innovative bioeconomy-related business models, products, and services.
- PHENET technologies will support farmers and breeders in increasing plant biomass quantity and quality, thus ensuring food security for Europe while adapting their businesses to climate change conditions and increasing their economic competitiveness.

Open Science Strategy:

- All four PHENET RIs jointly contribute to the development of the European Open Science Cloud as partners in the implementation projects EOSC-Life and ENVRI-FAIR.
- Open science is ensured through the data management services available on the experimental platforms, and open-source software access is provided either through dedicated websites or well-established software repositories.
- Training material on the application of PHENET technologies is designed, developed, and delivered according to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles. The Training material is deposited in open and well-known repositories to foster the adaptation and application by practitioners.

3. THE FUTURE BEYOND PHENET (2028 ONWARDS)

As PHENET will conclude in 2027, the intention is that the outcomes will have an enduring impact on science and economy around plant phenotyping, earth observation of agroecosystems, climate change resistance and mitigation, and agroecology transition. The technologies pioneered by PHENET will be integrated into the sustained service portfolios of AnaEE, ELIXIR, eLTER, and EMPHASIS, with the anticipation of substantial benefits for researchers and industry-leading towards increased competitiveness of Europe and climate-adapted food security.

4. FURTHER INFORMATION

- PHENET Website: <https://www.phenet.eu/en>